

IMPLEMENTATION OF A STRESS MANAGEMENT PROGRAM FOR JUNIOR COLLEGE STUDENTS AND STUDY ITS EFFICACY

Dr. Vidya Namdev Jadhav

Associate professor

M.V.P. Samaj's College of Education, Nashik

And

Dr. Shaikh Ejaz Ahmed Abdul Quddus

Assistant Professor

Masumiya College of Education, Ahmednagar

Abstract

Anything that poses a challenge or a threat to our well-being is a stress. When the stresses undermine both our mental and physical health they are bad. When we are stressed our blood pressure rises, breathing becomes more rapid, digestive system shows down, heart rate (pulse) rise, immune system goes down, muscles become tense, we do not sleep (heightened state of alertness), at some times when person gets hyper tension they make suicides.

Now days, students are facing with a number of stresses, both at college and outside of it. It has been suggested that adolescence is the worst possible time for students to be pressured into activities like academics, which can be as boring as they are important. However, most students are capable of dealing with the stress of school and college life if they know how to and if it is recognized as such. So, the teachers should give them the knowledge of stress management techniques. Present junior college students also not exception for it. So, they should know the techniques of stress management. They are also tomorrow's society maker and they have to handle social relations. If they get the knowledge of stress management they can decrease the stress of other. So, researchers decided to implement a Stress Management Program for junior college students and Study its Efficacy.

This paper focuses on the knowledge of stress management of junior college students which includes problem of research, operational definitions, objectives, assumptions, need and importance of research, hypothesis, method of research, sample, tools of research, nature of stress management program, data collection, data analysis, data interpretation, major findings and conclusions.

Implementation of a Stress Management Program for junior college Students and Study its Efficacy

1) Introduction

We generally use the word “stress” when we feel that everything seems to have become too much – we are overloaded and wonder whether we really can cope with the pressures placed upon us. Anything that poses a challenge or a threat to our well-being is a stress. When the stresses undermine both our mental and physical health they are bad.

When we are stressed our blood pressure rises, breathing becomes more rapid, digestive system shows down, heart rate (pulse) rise, immune system goes down, muscles become tense, we do not sleep (heightened state of alertness), at some times when person gets hyper tension they make suicides.

If we consider about teaching learning, there is much stress on students mind. The surveys show that many students go under hyper stress. There are many sources of student stress i.e. examinations, deadlines, returning to study, pressure of combining paid work and study, difficulty in organizing work, poor time management, leaving assignments to the last minute, out of control debts, poor housing, overcrowding, noise, adjusting to life in a new environment or even country, difficulties with personal relationships (e.g. splitting up), balancing the demands of a family with studying, parents or problems at home.

Now days, students are facing with a number of stresses, both at college and outside of it. It has been suggested that adolescence is the worst possible time for students to be pressured into activities like academics, which can be as boring as they are important. However, most students are capable of dealing with the stress of school and college life if they know how to and if it is recognized as such. So, the teachers should give them the knowledge of stress management techniques. Today's junior college students are tomorrow's citizens and they have to handle society, family and future generation. So, they should know the techniques of stress management. So, researchers decided to Implement a Stress Management Program for junior college students and Study its Efficacy.

2) Problem of the Research:

Implementation of a Stress Management Program for junior college students and Study its Efficacy

3) Operational Definitions:

i) A Stress Management Program:

The Program arranged for giving the knowledge of stress management to junior college students.

ii) Junior college students:

Junior college students are means the students who are studying in 11th and 12th standards.

iii) Efficacy:

Efficacy is the difference between the level of the knowledge of stress management before implementing the stress management program (pretest) and the level of the knowledge of stress management after implementing the stress management program (posttest).

4) Objectives of Research:

- 1) To know the level of knowledge of stress management amongst junior college students.
- 2) To prepare a 'stress management program' for giving the knowledge of stress management to junior college students.
- 3) To implement the 'stress management program' on the junior college students.
- 4) To study the efficacy of the 'stress management program'.

5) Assumptions of Research:

- 1) Junior college students face many problems and goes under a very dangerous situation of stress.
- 2) Junior college students do not know techniques of stress management.
- 3) In order to live healthy life stress management knowledge is essential for junior college students.

6) Need of research:

Junior college students come from different social strata. They have different social backgrounds. So, their problems are also different. There are many activities in junior college curriculum and they have to perform those activities. They get stress while performing those activities. Now a day's there is a lot of unemployment. Because of unemployment also junior college students gets stress and they should have the knowledge of stress management. Present junior college students are tomorrow's citizens and society. In order to decrease the tension of their family and society they should have the knowledge of stress management. Present research helps them to guide about stress management.

7) Importance of research:

Present research is very important for giving the knowledge of stress management to junior college students. It helps them to guide for decreasing stress. Because of that they will have healthy mind. The persons having healthy mind can keep their body healthy. Today's junior college students are tomorrow's nation builders. So, tomorrow's citizens will be healthy. Because of them society also will be healthy and active. So, this research is very important for create a healthy and stress less social atmosphere. Because of this students also will be healthy and stress less. It results to decrease suicides of students, which is a very major problem before the world. So, present research is very important.

8) Hypothesis:

There will be significant difference between the level of knowledge about stress management found in pre-test and the level of knowledge about stress management found in post-test.

9) Method of Research :

In present research the researchers have selected the experimental method of research. Here in the present research the main aim is to study the efficacy of Implementation of a stress management program for junior college students.

Experimental Design:

For present research the researcher has selected single group pretest and posttest design.

10) Sample:

The researcher has selected 40 junior college students from Mother Teresa junior college. The researcher has selected the sample by using Probability sampling based Simple Random Sampling method.

11) Tools of Research:**11.1 Data Collection Tool: Questionnaires:**

For present study researcher has made one questionnaire based on stress management knowledge. The researcher has used it as pretest and posttest.

11.2 Statistical tools:

The researcher has used 'mean' value for statistical analysis of the data.

12) Nature of Stress Management Program:

Day	Activities
●	Pretest
1 st Day	Lecture on Stress Management
2 nd Day	Discussion on Stress and Stress Management
3 rd Day	Lecture on Time Management
4 th Day	Yogasana and Pranayam
5 th Day	Omkar and Meditation
6 th Day	Guidance and Counseling
7 th Day	Sharing Experiences and feelings
8 th Day	Teaching Exercises
9 th Day	Funny Games
10 th Day	Lecture on Entertainment Techniques
●	Posttest

13) Tabulation, Graphical Representation of Mean of Tests and its Interpretation:

Content	M1(Mean of Pretest)	M2(Mean of Posttest)
Test based on stress management knowledge	07	16

Data Interpretation of Pretest and Posttest:

The M1 (Mean of Pretest) is 07 it means that the average score of total students in pretest is 07. The M2 (Mean of Posttest) is 16 it means that the average score of total students in posttest is 16. The score in posttest is increased than pretest. So, we can say that because of stress management program junior college students improved their level of knowledge about stress management.

• Graphical Representation of Mean of Tests

• Interpretation of graph:

There is significant difference in M1 (Mean of Pretest) and M2 (Mean of Posttest) because M1 is 07 and M2 is 16.

14) Major Findings:

1. Major Findings in Pretest :

The pretest was completely based on the knowledge of stress management. Junior college students did not have the sufficient knowledge about stress management. So, their average score of the pretest was only 07 Mean.

2. Major Findings in Posttest :

This test was also based on the knowledge of stress management. Junior college students' knowledge about stress management was improved than pretest. So, their average score of the posttest was 16 Mean.

Difference between both Means is 09. So, we can say that there is significant difference between pretest and posttest scores.

15) Conclusions:

1. The Stress Management program prepared by the researcher was effective to acquire the knowledge of stress management for junior college students.
2. The effect of the Stress Management program prepared by the researcher was positive for giving stress management knowledge to junior college students.
3. The knowledge of stress management of junior college students is improved due to implementation of the Stress Management program prepared by researcher.

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